

Temporal nature and recycling of Upper Paleolithic artifacts: the burned tools from the Molí del Salt site (Vimbodí i Poblet, northeastern Spain)

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Recent research in Paleolithic archeology has stressed the importance of temporal issues in assemblage interpretation. Archeological assemblages are temporal constructs, formed by the addition of an unknown number of depositional events. This temporal dimension is also evident at the artifactual level, since single artifacts may undergo different events of modification and/or uses over time. The recycling of previously discarded blanks for tool production is one of the best examples of the temporal nature of artifacts. The aim of this paper is to evaluate the importance of recycling in a Late Upper Paleolithic site, examining a type of artifact e burned tools e that has up to now been little used to approach this issue. Our results suggest that recycling was probably a significant component of Upper Paleolithic provisioning behavior, with important implications in site formation processes and the typological variability of assemblages. The expedient or curated character of recycling is also discussed.

1. Introduction

Recent developments in Paleolithic research have underscored the temporal nature of the archeological record. Most Paleolithic assemblages are palimpsests defined by stratigraphic criteria and are aggregates made up of remains from an unknown number of depositional events (Bailey, 2007; Bailey and Galadinou, 2009; Brochier, 1999; Malinsky-Buller et al., 2011; Vaquero, 2008). Although the exact duration of such formation processes cannot be established, it is possible that most Pleistocene assemblages accumulated over the course of hundreds or thousands of years. This cumulative character has important consequences in interpreting archeological assemblages, especially when attempting to apply ethnographically-derived middle-range theories constructed in high resolution temporal contexts. Events of different natures can contribute to these palimpsests and assemblages should therefore not be considered as coherent constructs from a functional, economical or cultural point of view. Time averaging explanations of the assemblage as-a-whole may thus be seriously flawed (Crema et al., 2010; Domínguez-Rodrigo, 2009; Lyman, 2003; Shott, 2008).

The significance of the temporal dimension in understanding archeological assemblages is widely recognized, but there is another time-related issue that has received comparatively less attention by archeologists: the temporal nature of single artifacts. Some artifacts may exhibit complex life histories characterized by the succession of different use and/or manufacture events. The meaning of such artifacts may differ through time (Bailey, 2007; Joy, 2009) and the final form, which is the outcome of the successive modifications, may be very different from that imposed in the first manufacture event. In these cases, artifact morphology should not be considered as the expression of mental templates imposed by the artisan, but the unplanned consequence of this sequence of modification events. The relevance of artifact biographies for interpreting variability in lithic assemblages was clearly pointed out by Harold L. Dibble (1991, 1995) in his studies on Middle Paleolithic sidescrapers. According to Dibble, the morphology of some Mousterian sidescrapers e and therefore their typological classification e was the result of several episodes of resharpening and use. Some artifacts were more intensely utilized and their edges were rejuvenated several times, while others were discarded after short use periods. These different life histories determined the appearance of different morphotypes, therefore playing a primary role in assemblage variability. These arguments are less common in Upper Paleolithic studies. Although resharpening has been used to explain the size variability of some tool types, like endscrapers (Movius et al., 1968; Morrow, 1997; Blades, 2003), it is normally assumed that modifications through time did not change the typological classification of retouched artifacts.

However, resharpening is not the sole expression of the temporal nature of lithic artifacts. Recycling is another behavior that implies successive stages of modification and/or use of the same artifact. Although the archeological consequences of resharpening and recycling may be difficult to distinguish, they are different behaviors that can be explained by entirely different factors. Resharpening is a maintenance procedure aimed at extending the use life of an artifact. It can be considered an economic behavior which is especially useful in contexts characterized by a shortage of raw materials, in which it is costly to discard worn-out artifacts. Unlike resharpening, recycling is defined by a phase of discard between the different use events. It is not the extension of the use life of the artifact, but the beginning of a new use life. Recycling has often been explained as the consequence of raw material scarcity, a way of maximizing the profitability of lithic resources (Kelly, 1988; Dibble and Rolland, 1992; Close, 1996; Amick, 2007; Galup, 2007; Hiscock, 2009). In this sense, recycling would be expected in curated technologies and it has even been considered as one of the main aspects of curation (Bamforth, 1986). However, it can also appear in expedient contexts, as a way to quickly meet immediate needs. Therefore, recycling should not be associated solely with curated contexts.

In spite of its potential significance in assemblage formation and artifact morphology, recycling behavior is particularly difficult to identify from archeological data. As some researchers point out (Amick, 2007; Galup, 2007), recycling was probably more common in prehistoric times than the scarce archeological evidence suggests. Due to these empirical problems, it has even been suggested that recycling is not a useful concept in archeological interpretation (Odell, 1996).

Archaeologists have used different kinds of data to identify recycling. Recycling can be approached by means of artifact movements inferred from spatial distribution and refitting (Vaquero, 2011). In this context, the differential scattering of reduction sequences can be used to establish temporal relationships between artifacts. In other cases, the use of a single artifact for different functions (for

example, a cobble first used as a hammerstone and later exploited as a core) has been considered evidence of recycling (Thiébaud et al., 2010). However, most approaches to recycling are based on artifact attributes, and especially on surface alterations, that suggest a period of discard between different activity events. These alterations can be considered as temporal markers, since they allow those events previous to the alteration to be distinguished from those that occurred afterwards. Obsidian hydration is a good indicator of recycling, since the thickness of hydration rinds depends on exposure length (Michels, 1969). Identifying rinds of different thicknesses on the same artifact is therefore an indication of recycling (Amick, 2007). Likewise, patinated flint artifacts are suitable for inferring recycling. In artifacts showing a double patina, the secondary modifications can be clearly differentiated from the older patinated surface. This has been the criterion most commonly used for identifying recycling in Paleolithic assemblages (cf. Barkai et al., 2009: 66; Debenath, 1992: 55; Galili and Weinstein-Evron, 1985: 40; Mora et al., 2004: 428; Nishiaki, 1985: 221e222). Both hydration bands and patina need considerable time to form and are perhaps the best criteria for identifying long-term recycling.

Fire damage is another temporal marker that provides clues as to what happened before and after it, although it has been less frequently used than hydration and patina in recycling studies. The effects of thermal alteration on fine-grained rocks has been widely analyzed in experimental studies and several kinds of macroscopic modifications e color changes, potlid fractures, fragmentation, and crazing e have been identified (Griffiths et al., 1986; Olausson and Larsson, 1982; Patterson, 1995; Purdy and Brooks, 1971; Sergant et al., 2006). The intensity of fire damage depends on temperature and exposure time, but experimental studies indicate that heat damage appears only at around 300 C in artifacts that come into direct contact with fire (Sergant et al., 2006). Modifications made after fire exposure are macroscopically identifiable due to the greasy luster on surfaces flaked subsequent to heat damage. Artifacts with such lustrous flake scars might be interpreted as the result of recycling, since burned blanks may correspond to previously discarded items that were unintentionally exposed to fire and later recycled to manufacture tools.

The main analytical problem lies in differentiating between items burnt after disposal from those intentionally exposed to fire in order to improve their flaking qualities. This obstacle might explain why the contribution of burnt artifacts to the discussion on recycling remains a relatively unexplored line of research. Several authors have defined the conditions and methods for heat treating (Crabtree and Butler, 1964; Mandeville, 1973; Griffiths et al., 1986; Domanski et al., 1994; Mercieca and Hiscock, 2008). Heat treatment improves the knappability of siliceous stones through the removal of interstitial water. This behavior has been noted in ethnographic contexts (Hester, 1972) and has been identified in some Paleolithic assemblages, particularly in the manufacture of tools that require relatively high technical skill. For example, the thermal preparation of flint was used in the manufacture of Solutrean points in Parpalló Cave (Tiffagom, 2006). However, determining the intentional nature of this heat treatment is not always straightforward and the accidental burning of lithics cannot be ruled out in some cases (Gregg and Grybush, 1976). In addition, thermal treatment seems superfluous for the manufacture of most Upper Paleolithic tools, which do not require high technical skill and are commonly made on unburned blanks. In this context, the typological distribution of tools retouched after fire damage can provide insight into the use of an intentional heat treatment. If the most skill-demanding tools show higher indices of post-damage retouch, intentional heat treatment would be supported.

The aim of this paper is to evaluate the relevance of recycling in Upper Paleolithic assemblages through the analysis of burned tools from Molí del Salt, a Late Upper Paleolithic site located in the northeastern Iberian Peninsula. We will try to establish whether recycling was a significant factor in the formation of the lithic assemblage. A method for measuring recycling will be proposed for comparing the importance of this behavior in different assemblages. We will pay special attention to the typological distribution of post-damage tools in order to ascertain the role of recycling in the typological variability of assemblages. Typological differences between post-damage retouched tools and the rest of the tools in an assemblage may be useful not only in defining the activity context of recycling, but also in distinguishing recycling from an intentional heat treatment. Multiple tools are of particular interest, as they may be the product of either an intentional design or, alternatively, the addition over time of different tools on the same blank. A higher index of recycling among multiple tools would support the temporal nature of these artifacts. Finally, we will discuss the economic meaning of recycling and its association with either curated or expedient technical strategies. Due to the economic implications of recycling, differences throughout the archeological sequence may also be indicative of temporal changes in raw material provisioning constraints or settlement patterns.

2. Materials and methods

The Moli del Salt site is located in the village of Vimbodí i Poblet, 35 km northwest of the city of Tarragona (Fig. 1), at 490 m above sea level on the left bank of the Milans, a small tributary of the Francolí river. It is a rockshelter in the Tertiary conglomerates (Upper Oligocene) common along the eastern borders of the Ebro basin. Archeological excavations begun in 1999 revealed a 2.5 m thick stratigraphic sequence containing Mesolithic and Late Upper Paleolithic (Late Magdalenian) layers. The Late Upper Paleolithic sequence corresponds to the lowermost 1.5 m of the stratigraphy, a succession of silty and sandy layers with some large conglomerate blocks, in which two main stratigraphic and archeological units have been distinguished from top to bottom: unit A, subdivided into levels Asup, A and A1; and unit B, subdivided into levels B1 and B2. An Early Holocene Mesolithic layer at the top of the sequence will not be included in this study. Several ¹⁴C/AMS dates have been obtained for levels Asup and A (Table 1), ranging from 10,840 ± 50 ¹⁴C years BP e from 12,690 to 13,800 cal years BP. Levels B1 and B2 have been dated respectively to 11,940 ± 100 and 12,510 ± 100 ¹⁴C years BP e 14,070 ± 13,590 and 15,300 ± 14,540 cal years BP. The upper layers (Asup and A) have been extensively excavated, but levels A1, B1 and B2 have been exclusively documented in a 3 m² test pit. The number of remains in these levels is therefore much lower than in the uppermost one. The archeological assemblages from the Molí del Salt site are characterized by ample evidence of burning. Burned remains are common in both the lithic and faunal assemblages. This may be explained by the hearth-focused nature of human occupations, but the characteristics of the stratigraphic succession also played an important role. The

Paleolithic sequence of this site is a large palimpsest formed by a 1.5 m thick deposit of sands and silts without sterile layers. This means that hearths were systematically constructed over the lithics and bones discarded during previous occupations. In such a context, post-depositional and unintentional fire damage would be common.

Flint is overwhelmingly dominant in the lithic assemblages and it was practically the only raw material used in knapping activities. Although some tools on limestone and schist have also been identified, only flint tools have been considered in this paper. The technological and typological characteristics are typical of Late Upper Paleolithic assemblages in Mediterranean Spain. In general, toolkits are dominated by endscrapers, backed elements (points and blades) and denticulates, although other types (burins, borers, abrupts, truncations) are also relatively well represented. However, there are significant differences between the archeological units. Truncations are particularly common in unit B, where they show percentage values of around 20%, but they are very scarce in unit A. Burins show the opposite trend; they are well represented in unit A, but practically absent in unit B. Endscrapers exhibit their maximum values in unit A, while in unit B their percentage is similar to that of truncations. Other types (denticulates, backed artifacts) do not show significant changes throughout the sequence. These changes are associated with other evolutionary trends in raw material provisioning (local raw materials increase from bottom to top) and artifact size (tools tend to get smaller over time).

We have identified burned tools using the different macroscopic features described in the literature as evidence of fire damage in flint artifacts. According to the incidence of burning, four kinds of artifacts have been distinguished among the retouched implements recovered at Molí del Salt: a) tools without fire damage; b) tools retouched before fire damage; c) tools retouched after fire damage; and d) tools that were retouched both before and after fire damage. The two latter categories have been identified through the presence of retouch scars whose surface is different from the rest of the blank surface, generally because they display a greasy luster (Fig. 2). These are the artifacts that can be directly associated with recycling, since they indicate the modification of previously burned blanks. The artifacts were divided into size categories according to length and width: very small (<500 mm²), small (500e1000 mm²), medium (1000e1500 mm²), large (1500e2000 mm²) and very large (>2000 mm²).

The retouched artifacts were analyzed and classified in keeping with the Structural and Analytical Typology of G. Laplace (1972), although only their adscription to the main typological groups will be used in this paper. However, we have also included a typological group that does not appear in Laplace's typology: retouched blanks. This group contains artifacts that have been retouched on one side, but that lack the formalized morphology characteristic of the other typological groups. We have paid special attention to the distinction between simple tools, i.e. artifacts bearing only one tool type, and multiple tools, which display evidence of more than one tool type manufactured on a single blank. It is important to stress that we have considered one of the types of simple endscrapers defined by Laplace e the endscraper with lateral retouch e as a multiple tool, since it is characterized by two retouched sides with different characteristics.

A Minimum Recycling Index (MRI) was calculated as an estimate of the significance of recycling in tool production. This index corresponds to the percentage of burned tools that were retouched after fire damage. This must be considered as a minimum index because we do not know if some artifacts retouched before burning were also manufactured from recycled blanks. As for the unburned tools, we cannot say if the artifacts burned after retouch were previously recycled or not. We cannot therefore rule out that the actual number of recycled items is higher than that deduced from our data. Although it is only an approximation to the real incidence of recycling, this MRI essentially serves for comparative purposes, as it allows the differential practice of recycling among different assemblages to be estimated.

3. Results

We analyzed 1583 retouched artifacts from the Late Upper Paleolithic layers, 1383 of them corresponding to simple tools and 199 to multiple tools. As shown in Table 2, the artifacts that do not show macroscopic evidence of fire damage are dominant (62.6%), although there is a significant proportion of burned tools. However, differences between levels are important and the percentage of burned artifacts tends to be higher in the levels of unit A. The effects of sample size cannot be dismissed in the explanation of these differences, but it is worth pointing out that the percentage of burned tools in level A1, which is the smallest assemblage, is similar to that obtained in the other levels of unit A. Natural formation processes may explain the different proportion of burned artifacts in units A and B. According to the geoarcheological study (Vallverdú and Carrancho, 2004), the sedimentary processes in unit B took place at a faster rate than in unit A. As a consequence, the artifacts were more rapidly buried and therefore less exposed to thermal damage.

Artifacts manufactured after fire damage account for 7.5% of the retouched tools (Figs. 3 and 4). If there was not a preferential selection of burned blanks for recycling, a similar proportion should be expected among the unburned artifacts. This percentage represents a Minimum Index of Recycling of 20.4. Both levels A_{sup} and A exhibit a similar MRI (20.5 and 20.7 respectively). The MRI for levels A1 (21.7), B1 (20) and B2 (9) should be considered with caution due to the small sample size, although the indices for levels A1 and B1 are practically the same as those obtained in the two uppermost levels. Taken together, the MRI for unit B is 15.3, which is slightly lower than the index from unit A. This would suggest that the intensity of recycling was higher in unit A, but more artifacts need to be studied to corroborate this temporal trend.

As shown in Table 3, very small items are clearly dominant among the unburned and pre-damage tools, accounting for more than 50% of the artifacts. However, very small artifacts are less common among post-damage tools, which are characterized by an increase in small pieces. This underrepresentation of the smallest size class among the tools manufactured after heat damage may be explained by the lower visibility of the smallest blanks, which tend to be buried faster than larger objects.

As far as simple tools are concerned, endscrapers are the largest typological group (37.4%), followed by backed tools (19.4%), denticulates (12.5%) and retouched blanks (12.4%). The remaining tool types (abrupts, burins, borers, sidescrapers and truncations) are present in lower frequencies. As Table 4 shows, pre-damage and post-damage retouched implements are represented in all of the

typological groups. If only the artifacts retouched after fire damage are considered, the size of some typological groups is similar to that recorded in the assemblage as-a-whole, although others exhibit significant differences (Fig. 5). Backed tools are the second most common tool type in the whole assemblage, but they only amount to 3% among the post-damage tools. Retouched blanks show the opposite trend, their percentage in the post-damage assemblage is significantly higher (24.7%) than that recorded in the whole assemblage. There are also clear differences in terms of the representation of post-damage retouched tools inside each typological group. The highest percentages of post-damage artifacts are found among retouched blanks (13.9%) and borers (11.7%), which also show the highest MRI (32.8 and 33.3 respectively) (Table 5). On the other hand, backed elements and truncations exhibit the lowest indices of recycling (4 and 8.6 respectively). Only three backed tools and two truncations were manufactured on burned blanks. The scarce number of recycled truncations could be explained by the lower frequency of recycling in unit B, since truncations are abundant in these basal layers but uncommon in unit A. However, this is not the case with backed tools, which are well represented throughout the sequence. Therefore, it seems that these artifacts, normally interpreted as hunting armatures, were rarely made on burned blanks. We identified 199 double tools in the retouched assemblage (Table 6). They represent 12.5% of all the retouched artifacts (Fig. 6). A large proportion of these tools (55.7%) correspond to endscrapers with lateral retouch. Twenty-three artifacts were manufactured on burned blanks and fourteen of them exhibit both pre- and post-damage retouch. The percentage of recycled blanks is higher among double tools than in the whole tool assemblage (11.5% and 7% respectively). This difference is also evident when comparing the MRIs from simple and double tools (19 and 29.4 respectively), suggesting that the incidence of recycling is higher among double tools. If these data are extrapolated to the whole assemblage, this means that a significant percentage of double tools were not the result of an intentional design, but rather of recycling previously retouched blanks. The double tools retouched both before and after heat damage are particularly interesting, because the type of tool that was originally on the burned blank can be distinguished from the type added after burning. Of the 14 artifacts included in this group, 12 of them indicate that the post-damage retouch event is associated with an expedient tool type: a denticulate (five cases) or a retouched blank (seven cases). In the remaining two cases, the second tool type was an endscraper. This corroborates the preferential association of post-damage retouch with the less formalized tool types, as suggested by simple tools.

4. Discussion

Our results suggest that burned artifacts may provide a useful approach to the study of recycling in archeological contexts. However, the incidence of recycling obtained through this approach should be considered an underestimation of the actual importance of recycling. A tool manufactured on a burned blank can be said to be the product of recycling, but the opposite is not true. We cannot say that a tool made on an unburned blank or one burned after retouch was not the product of recycling, because in this case there is no temporal marker that would allow different and successive events to be distinguished. As a consequence, the absolute importance of this practice in assemblage formation remains elusive. In the Molí del Salt assemblage, we were able to establish that 7.5% of tools were produced on recycled blanks, but this does not mean that the remaining 92.5% of the blanks were not recycled. We simply do not know. The feasibility of this approach also depends on the abundance of burned artifacts available for study and therefore on site formation processes. It will be more useful in deposits characterized by the overlapping of occupation events in which hearths were constructed over remains discarded by previous visitors. In this sense, palimpsests characterized by slow sedimentary rhythms would be more suitable in the study of this kind of recycling than sedimentary contexts of higher resolution in which discarded artifacts were rapidly buried. Moreover, residential sites defined by activities focused around hearths would also be very suited to this approach.

The evidence provided by the burned tools of Molí del Salt suggests that the gathering of previously discarded blanks was possibly a common provisioning strategy during the Upper Paleolithic. Although the ethnographic data on lithic production are relatively scarce, this lithic scavenging matches the behavioral patterns observed among modern hunter-gatherers (Horne and Aiston, 1924; Kelly, 1934; Opler, 1946; Riddell, 1960; Smith, 1974; Gould, 1977). Both the ethnographic and the archeological studies tend to explain recycling as a response to raw material scarcity. As raw material availability can vary over time due to changes in mobility or subsistence patterns, temporal variations in the intensity of recycling can be expected accordingly. At Molí del Salt, the decreasing percentage of flint from distant sources from bottom to top has been interpreted as the result of changes in settlement patterns characterized by a reduction in the size of the home range. As a consequence, the increasing stress on local flint sources would lead to a more economizing behavior, as reflected in the decrease of mean tool size in the upper layers. A greater emphasis on recycling in the upper layers would be consistent with this picture. However, our data are inconclusive due to the scarce number of artifacts in the basal layers and we must wait for larger assemblages in order to verify this temporal trend.

As lithic resources were transported to occupation sites, those sites were in turn transformed into lithic provisioning points. In this context, provisioning decisions may have changed according to the availability and abundance of artifacts at the sites, especially comparing the first stages in the formation of the stratigraphic assemblage when the site was "empty", and the final stages, when the site offered plenty of resources abandoned by previous occupants. This can explain, for example, a part of the chert provisioning variability documented in the Middle Paleolithic of Abric Romani (Vaquero et al., 2012). The availability of artifacts for scavenging would be more conspicuous in large occupational palimpsests, associated with slow sedimentary rhythms. Although undocumented as of yet, we cannot rule out that some anthropic disturbances of sediments in archeological sites may be related to the search for usable lithic materials. As a consequence of lithic scavenging, recycling may be the source of some "cultural anomalies", like the appearance of Acheulean handaxes and cleavers in a Magdalenian layer (Corchón, 1993) or Early Holocene projectile points in a mid-Holocene assemblage (Amick, 2007). Moreover, this also has interesting consequences as far as the treatment of raw materials of different origins is concerned. One of the most straightforward conclusions of technological studies is that raw materials tend to be exploited and processed in different ways according to the distance to their respective provisioning areas. Exogenous materials coming from distant sources tend to be transported into the sites in a more elaborately altered form, whereas local raw materials gathered near the site are normally more expediently processed. As a consequence, the kind of tools made on exogenous and local

materials also tend to be different. However, this general principle may be biased by the phenomenon of recycling. Once transported to the site, exogenous materials become strictly local resources and, if scavenged for recycling, may be treated as local and used to manufacture local tool types.

All the typological groups contain artifacts retouched after heat damage. There is no evidence of the preferential use of burned blanks for the manufacture of tools requiring high technical performance, as expected in the case of an intentional heat treatment. In general, most of the lithic tools found in the Molí del Salt assemblage are easily made through direct percussion flaking and they were usually produced on unburned blanks. In fact, the types with the highest MRIs (retouched blanks, borers, denticulates) can be considered expedient tools that do not involve an elaborate formal design or planning depth. In this context, recycling seems the most parsimonious explanation for the use of heated blanks in the production of tools. In fact, we think that recycling cannot be ruled out in some instances in which an intentional thermal treatment has been proposed. For instance, intentional heat treatment has been suggested for the manufacture of Solutrean points in Parpalló Cave (Tiffagom, 2006). Intentional heating seems likely for some Solutrean points, but it is not clear for others. Among the leafshaped points there is a high proportion of artifacts retouched after fire damage (from 68 items, 16 were certainly manufactured on heated blanks). However, of the 98 barbed and tanged points studied by Tiffagom, heating before retouch was a certainty in only one artifact and likely in 14. In spite of the technical complexity of these artifacts and the use of pressure flaking, heating before retouch was not dominant and the proportion of probable postdamage tools was only slightly higher than that exhibited by some expedient tools e like retouched blanks, borers and denticulates e in Molí del Salt. This indicates that thermal treatment was not indispensable in the production of these artifacts and we think that recycling may be a more feasible explanation for the post-damage tools. In order to confirm an intentional heat treatment, a general approach to burned artifacts is needed to test if the most demanding artifacts are more commonly made on thermally damaged blanks. If this is not the case, the possibility of recycling cannot be dismissed.

We found that not all tools were equally manufactured on recycled items. According to the data we have presented here, backed tools and truncations were rarely produced on burned blanks. As mentioned earlier, truncations are abundant in the lower archeological layers (unit B), which seem to be characterized by lower recycling indexes. However, backed elements are well represented at all the stratigraphic levels and temporal changes in recycling intensity therefore cannot explain their low MRI. Backed tools were used as hunting armatures and were blades and bladelets blunted on one or two sides by small steep removals. The aerodynamic requirements related to their use as projectile tips and the need to fit a preexisting shaft cause a high degree of formal and metrical standardization, higher than those found in other tools. In addition, they can be considered a good example of a “reliable artifact” in the sense described by Bleed (1986), that is, they are designed to minimize the risk of failure in stressful situations. As a consequence, backed tools would be one of the most curated components in Late Upper Paleolithic technical systems. Furthermore, manufacture and use locations are clearly different, since projectile points have to be made in advance and their production process therefore has to be more planned and scheduled. Backed elements are more demanding in terms of the kind of blanks that are suitable for their manufacture, since they are made on blades or bladelets. The probability of finding a suitable blank among the previously discarded artifacts would be lower compared to other tools that can be made on any kind of blank. This is particularly true in a technical context like that of the Molí del Salt, in which blade/bladelet production is not dominant and blade/ bladelets represent less than 20% of the discarded blanks. It is particularly significant that of the three backed elements made on burned blanks, one of them is a backed point made on a naturally backed blade in which only a small part of the back has been shaped by retouch (Fig. 7). These partially backed points are unusual among backed elements and this underscores the expedient character of artifacts made on recycled items.

The Molí del Salt evidence suggests that recycling is more closely linked to domestic tools, which show a coincidence between the context of manufacture and the context of use and are less demanding in terms of the metrical and formal characteristics of the blanks used for their production. Recycling seems to be a way of meeting immediate needs. As mentioned earlier, the highest recycling indices are associated with the least formalized tools e retouched blanks, denticulates, abrupts e which supports the expedient nature of recycling. In this sense, recycling cannot be linked to a curated technology, since the most curated component of a technical system would be the least affected by recycling. On the contrary, as the expedient character of a technical system increases, a higher frequency of recycling should be expected. This brings additional support to the differences between recycling and resharpening, since the latter, aimed at extending the use life of artifacts, seems more likely in a curated context.

The higher incidence of recycling among double tools is particularly important in the interpretation of lithic assemblages, as it suggests that a high proportion of these tools were not the expression of well-defined mental templates. This is especially significant in Upper Paleolithic assemblages, in which it is normally assumed that artifacts were manufactured according to preconceived morphological designs. The degree of standardization exhibited by many Upper Paleolithic tool types indicates that such mental templates are beyond doubt in most instances. However, the temporal nature of at least some double tools suggests that artifact history is also an important factor in the typological variability of Upper Paleolithic assemblages. In this context, composite tools can be considered as indicative of an economizing or expedient behavior. We obviously need more cases to confirm this relationship between recycling and multiple tools. However, if this is corroborated by additional data, the proportion of multiple tools could therefore be considered as a proxy of recycling in assemblages in which this practice cannot be identified by other methods.

5. Conclusions

The study of burned tools from the Molí del Salt site suggests that fire damaged artifacts may be a useful approach towards understanding the phenomenon of recycling in Paleolithic assemblages. Our data indicate that recycling was an important component in the technological behavior of Late Upper Paleolithic huntergatherers. Although the recycling indices derived from burned artifacts should be considered an underestimation of the actual importance of recycling, the Molí del Salt data indicate that a significant proportion of tools are associated with the scavenging of previously discarded blanks. The use of sites as lithic provisioning points was probably an additional reason for the reoccupation of sites over the millennia, but at the same time such

temporal dynamics changed the relationships between the site and its landscape, at least as far as lithic provisioning is concerned. Regardless of geological origin, all lithics should be considered as local once discarded at the site. In such a context, provisioning behavior would be less constrained by the distribution of primary raw material sources. The correlation of recycling with long-term trends associated with an increasing emphasis on economizing behaviors, although outlined in this paper, remains an open question and will be the subject of further research.

The Molí del Salt data have also provided some insight into the technical context associated with recycling, especially concerning the relationship between recycling and curation. Contrary to previous assumptions, recycling does not seem to be related to curated technologies, but would be rather more common in expedient situations typical of domestic contexts. It would be an easy form of supplying blanks as needs arose in situations in which tool manufacture and use were carried out in the same place. Recycling was particularly suitable for the production of expedient tools that demanded little in terms of blank form or/and size. On the other hand, reliable tools that required a more scheduled production and were made on specific kinds of blanks were rarely manufactured on recycled artifacts. The importance of recycling is therefore conditioned by the organization of technology. It should become less common as the number of curated components increase in a technical system.

Recycling appears as just another dimension of the dynamic and temporal nature of archeological entities, both assemblages and single artifacts, and emphasizes the need to “temporalize” interpretations in order to understand the behavioral significance of assemblages. Although it seems clear that many Upper Paleolithic tool types correspond to well-defined mental templates, the morphology of some artifacts may be the unplanned outcome of different and successive modification events. The artifacts that were retouched both before and after thermal damage indicate that this may be the case in particular with multiple tools, especially those in which the presence of a formalized tool type e endscraper, burin, truncation e is associated with a more expedient and unformalized tool type. Increasing proportions of expedient and multiple tools would therefore be the consequence of a growing emphasis on recycling in the archeological record. However, additional studies on burned tools will be needed in order to verify whether these are general trends in Upper Paleolithic industries or if they are restricted to specific chronological or geographical contexts.

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Fig. 1. A. Moli del Salt location in the northwestern corner of the Iberian Peninsula. B. General view of the site during the 2003 excavation season.

Table 1

¹⁴C AMS dates from Moli del Salt. C ages have been converted to calendar ages by using CalPal2007-HULU Calibration Curve in the CalPal calibration software.

Level	Ref. lab.	Material	14C age (BP)	Error (±)	Years cal BP (2σ)	Years cal BC (2σ)
Sup	Beta-173335	Bone	8040	40	9110–8710	7160–6760
Asup	Beta-179595	Charcoal	10840	50	12890–12690	10940–10740
Asup	Beta-179598	Charcoal	10990	50	13050–12730	11100–10780
Asup	Beta-221912	Charcoal	11060	70	13130–12770	11800–10820
Asup	Beta-221913	Charcoal	10850	70	12950–12670	11000–10720
Asup	Beta-235268	Charcoal	10920	60	12990–12710	11040–10760
A	Beta-235267	Charcoal	11000	60	13080–12720	11300–10770
A	Beta-277000	Charcoal	11230	50	13270–13030	11320–11080
A	Beta-277001	Charcoal	11440	60	13500–13180	11550–11230
A	Beta-284214	Charcoal	10940	50	12990–12710	11040–10760
A	Beta-284212	Charcoal	11770	50	13790–13550	11840–11600
A	Beta-284213	Charcoal	11800	50	13800–13560	11850–11610
B1	Gifa-101037	Charcoal	11940	100	14070–13590	12120–11640
B2	Gifa-101038	Charcoal	12510	100	15300–14540	13350–12590

Fig. 2. Endscraper retouched after fire damage. Close-up of the retouched edge showing the greasy luster characteristic of post-damage retouch.

Table 2
 Distribution of retouched artifacts by archeological levels and fire damage categories.

Archaeological level	No fire damage (n)	No fire damage (%)	Damage after retouch (n)	Damage after retouch (%)	Damage before retouch (n)	Damage before retouch (%)	Damage before and after retouch (n)	Damage before and after retouch (%)	Total (n)	Total (%)
Asup	281	61,6	139	30,4	30	6,5	6	1,3	456	100
A	577	61,1	291	30,8	61	6,4	15	1,5	944	100
A1	31	57,4	18	33,3	5	9,2			54	100
B1	52	77,6	12	17,9	2	2,9	1	1,4	67	100
B2	51	82,2	10	16,1	1	1,6			62	100
Total	992	62,6	470	29,6	99	6,2	22	1,3	1583	100

Fig. 3. Tools retouched after fire damage. White lines indicate the location of the retouched edges. 1, 5. Retouched blanks. 2. Endscraper with lateral retouch. 3, 4, 6. Endscrapers. 1 and 2 were retouched both before and after fire damage.

Fig. 4. Endscrapers retouched after fire damage.

Table 4

Distribution of simple tools according to typological groups and fire damage categories. Only the most represented typological groups have been included in this table. Thirteen artifacts ascribed to very poorly represented groups (bitruncations, points and pieces with flat retouch) have been excluded.

Typological group	No fire damage	Damage after retouch	Damage before retouch	Damage before and after retouch	Total
Abrupts	43	21	6	e	70
	61.4	30.0	8.5	e	100
Burins	28	17	2	1	48
	58.3	35.4	4.1	2.0	100
Borers	22	8	3	1	34
	64.7	23.5	8.8	2.9	100
Denticulates	103	53	16	e	172
	59.5	30.6	9.2	e	100
Endscrapers	309	167	35	3	514
	60.1	32.4	6.8	0.5	100
Backed tools	191	72	2	1	266
	71.8	27.0	0.7	0.3	100
Sidescrapers	11	3	1	e	15
	73.3	20.0	6.6	e	100
Retouched blanks	98	49	22	2	171
	57.3	28.6	12.8	1.1	100
Truncations	58	21	2	e	81
	71.6	25.9	2.4	e	100
Total	863	411	89	8	1371
	62.9	29.9	6.4	0.5	100

Table 5
 Percentage of simple tools retouched after thermal damage and Minimum Recycling Index for each typological group.

Typological group	Percentage of post-damage tools	Minimum Recycling Index
Abrupts	8.5	22.2
Burins	6.1	15.0
Borers	11.7	33.3
Denticulates	9.3	23.1
Endscrapers	7.3	18.5
Backed tools	1	4
Sidescrapers	6.6	25
Retouched blanks	13.9	32.8
Truncations	2.4	8.6
Total	7	19

Fig. 5. Bar graph showing the percentage of each typological group in the three fire damage categories.

Table 6

Distribution of double tools according to typological groups and fire damage categories.

Typological group	No fire damage (n)	Damage after retouch (n)	Damage before retouch (n)	Damage before and after retouch (n)	Total (n)
Abrupt–denticulates	4		2		7
Abrupt–truncation	1				1
Borer–denticulates	1				1
Borer–endscraper	3				3
Borer–sidescraper			1		1
Borer–truncation	1				1
Burin–burin	9		1		10
Burin–denticulates	5		2	1	9
Burin–endscraper	1		1		2
Burin–sidescraper	2		1		3
Denticulates–denticulates	6			1	10
Denticulates–endscraper	4		4		9
Denticulates–sidescraper	5		2		7
Denticulates–retouched blank				2	2
Endscraper–endscraper	9		3	1	14
Endscraper–backed blade	1				1
Endscraper–sidescraper				1	1
Endscraper–retouched blank	64		37	5	111
Endscraper–truncation	4		1		5
Truncation–truncation	1				1
Total	121		55	9	199

Fig. 6. Double tools retouched before and after fire damage. 1. Endscrapereendscraper. 2. Endscraperretouched blank. 3. Endscraperedenticulate. 4. Denticulateedenticulate. 5. Endscraperedenticulate.

Fig. 7. Backed point retouched after fire damage. Retouched is limited to the distal end of the point. This expedient procedure for manufacturing backed tools is uncommon at Molí del Salt.